

Joint EUFEPS - SITELF meeting

ADVANCES IN PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

May **27 | 29**
2026

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POS.158: 3D-printed microfluidic platform for sustainable natural gum-stabilized emulsions

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POS.158

3D-printed microfluidic platform for sustainable natural gum-stabilized emulsions
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3D-printed microfluidic platform for sustainable natural gum-stabilized emulsions

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Growing concerns regarding the safety and environmental impact of synthetic surfactants have accelerated interest in natural polysaccharides as sustainable emulsion stabilizers [1]. Droplet-based microfluidics offers precise, low-energy and material-efficient emulsification, enabling controlled formation of monodisperse droplets suitable for pharmaceutical and cosmetic formulations [2]. Therefore, we aimed to evaluate the feasibility of microchannel emulsification for producing oil-in-water (O/W) emulsions stabilized with tragacanth gum (TG), guar gum (GG) or gum arabic (GA), and to relate droplet formation behavior to physicochemical properties of the continuous phases.

Nine aqueous gum solutions (0.05–0.25% w/w) were prepared and characterized by surface tension and specific viscosity measurements. O/W emulsions (oil:water = 1:2) were generated using a custom 3D-printed flow-focusing microfluidic chip with controlled phase flow rates. Droplet formation and generation frequency were quantified by optical microscopy and video analysis.

Increasing gum concentration reduced surface tension and increased specific viscosity of the continuous phases. Stable oil droplet formation was achieved with TG and GG solutions across the investigated range, whereas GA failed to produce discrete droplets under identical conditions. Droplet generation frequency was higher for TG than GG and showed a strong positive correlation with gum concentration and a strong negative correlation with surface tension. These findings indicate that interfacial activity is the dominant factor governing droplet breakup in the applied microfluidic regime.

Flow-focusing microfluidic emulsification using low-concentration natural gums is a promising sustainable approach for producing O/W emulsions, since TG and GG demonstrated effective stabilization in the 0.05–0.25% range. The combination of natural polysaccharides and 3D-printed microfluidic devices represents a green and controllable platform for future pharmaceutical and cosmetic emulsion design.

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Literature:

[1] Xu Y, et al. *Int J Biol Macromol.* 2025, 293, 139420.

[2] Su W, et al. *Rev Chem Eng.* 2024, 40(3), 401-434.